

Table 3. Summary of major synthesis methods for carbon-based nano-materials, highlighting differences in process conditions, advantages, limitations and suitability for industrial integration.

Synthesis Method	Typical Products	Key Advantages	Key Limitations	Industrial Scalability Outlook	Ref.
CVD	Graphene, CNTs, CNWs, GNRs, GQDs, NDs, graphitic foams	Precise morphology control; tunable gas chemistry; compatibility with wafer-scale substrates; direct growth on device surfaces; high structural uniformity; plasma-enabled low-T synthesis	High gas consumption; moderate throughput; requires temperature management; sensitive to precursor ratios	High potential: already used in roll-to-roll graphene film production; adaptable to CMOS-compatible low-T PECVD; strong pathway to industrial adoption	[12,101,153,159, 160]
Arc Discharge	CNTs, fullerenes, CNOs	High crystallinity; simple apparatus; good for bulk powder production	Poor morphology control; limited tunability; high temperatures; not substrate-compatible	Moderate, but mostly for bulk powders; unsuitable for device integration	[12]
Hydrothermal/Solvothermal	CQDs, CNTs,	Scalable; low temperature; solution processable; easy doping	Poor crystallinity; surface-state-dominated PL; difficult to integrate with solid-state devices	High for inks and coatings; low for device-grade graphitic materials	[161]
Electrochemical Exfoliation	GQDs, CNTs,	Room-temperature; fast; high yield	Produces defected or oxidized structures; broad size distribution	Medium, largely for inks and composites	[162]
Template-Assisted Pyrolysis	GQDs, CNTs,	Good morphological replication; tunable geometry	Requires template removal; limited crystallinity; slower throughput	Medium depending on template cost and manufacturing process	[163]